

Bank Regulations and Their Effects on Banks' Profitability: A Literature Review

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Abstract: This paper reviews the relevant literature on the impact of regulation and supervision on the profitability of banks. The paper reviews and critically analyses the theoretical and empirical literature on the relationship between regulations and profitability and their effect on the banks' risk profile. Considering the outcomes, findings and recommendations from studies as articulated in the literature reviewed, it is comprehensible that the impact of regulation and supervision on banking activities varies and appears to be hybrid and context specific to the period and sample under consideration. Such rules appear to evolve naturally according to economic and financial contexts and per country.

Keywords: banks, profitability, risk profile, regulation; supervision

I. INTRODUCTION

Regulation of banks refers to a set of rules or agreed behaviour imposed by governments, external agencies or industry bodies (Llewellyn, 1986). Regulations impose boundaries in the way banks perform their business activities, and therefore are bound to have some impacts on their balance sheets and income statements. Foot (2003) further defines bank supervision as the process of monitoring banks to ensure that they are carrying out their business activities in accordance with laws, rules and regulations.

Vitas (1990) pronounced that good regulation and supervision minimise the negative impact of moral hazard and price shocks on the banking system, thereby leading to a reduction in bank failures and banking system distress. Usually, the role of banks, whether in developed or developing economies, consists of financial intermediation, provision of an efficient payments system and serving as a way for the implementation of monetary policies. The business of banking involves taking calculated risks and minimising losses to make profits for the banks' shareholders (Rossouw, 2009).

The strategy that banks embark on in response to regulations and supervision in a fast changing regulatory and supervisory framework challenges banks to act informatively. The profitability among banks is subject to factors in both the macro and micro economic variables in the form of banking regulations, policies and supervisory frameworks imposed by various regulators, supervisors, governments, and policymakers in countries across the world. The imposition of regulations, policies and supervision is an attempt by countries to protect their economies and individual depositors to banks (Caruana, 2015). Nanda and Panda (2018) expressed that the level of bank profitability is influenced by the intensity of its income generation activities such as lending and trading of forex.

PURPOSE

The purpose of this paper is to review and analyse the literature on the effect of regulation and supervision of banks on their profitability, in the context of the paucity of the literature in Africa.

II. BACKGROUND TO BANKING REGULATION AND SUPERVISION

Discussions around the regulations and supervision of the financial sector has been ongoing for decades, however the 2008 to 2009 global financial crisis has amplified the discussions and debates among researchers and policymakers. The discussions were also exacerbated by the evolution of the financial sector as economies globalised and financial markets integrated worldwide. According to Botha and Makina (2011), one of the causes of the global financial crisis, often cited, is inadequate or improper regulation and supervision of the financial sector. The researchers argued that the crisis

exposed the existence of inadequate regulatory frameworks which could not keep up with developments in the globalised environment. This persuaded developed economies to reform their financial regulations and supervision with the United Kingdom and other major European economies implementing the Twin Peak strategy and the United State of America enacting the Dodd-Frank Act (Botha & Makina, 2011). Countries are adopting frameworks in line with the development in financial systems and economic environment globally.

Due to the vital role that banks play in the growth of the economies of various countries worldwide, the sector receives regulatory attention from industry, home countries and international bodies. The intention is to mitigate against the overall systemic risks to the economy that could arise from bank failures. A suggestion is that countries should take regulation and supervision seriously in an attempt to maintain the stability and health of the banking sector and the financial system in general.

However, Carney (2017) warned the Group of 20 countries (G20) that a decade on from the global financial crisis of 2008/2009, policymakers and regulators are starting to tire of imposing a seemingly endless drip-feed of new rules on financial services firms. Carney further warned that giving in to reform fatigue, could hamper international regulatory cooperation, create inefficiencies and friction, reduce competition and hinder investment flows. Carney's arguments could be construed to push for an increase in regulations in the banking sector worldwide. The attestation to investment flows is pertinent when the theory is applied in Africa. The continent does not appear to be reaping the investment flows as a result of the implementation of new stringent regulations such as those that are imposed under the Basel framework. In addition, the cost of compliance 2017 Report (an annual survey of almost 900 financial services compliance professionals worldwide conducted by information services provider Thomson Reuters), found that seven out of ten respondents expected the focus on managing regulatory risk to increase in 2017, while 20% expected the focus to be significantly greater. This reflects the views that the stakeholders in the banking industry are observing with regard to the effect of regulation and supervision on the activities of banks.

Heimler (2006) traced the history of banking regulation and found that its origination from concerns within the microeconomic environment over the ability of bank creditors to monitor the risks originating on the lending side and from both the micro and macroeconomic concerns over the stability of the banking system in the case of a bank crisis. In addition, Heimler (2006) understood that further to the statutory and administrative regulatory provisions, the banking sector has been subject to widespread "informal" regulations, such as, governments' use of their discretion, outside formalised legislation, to influence the banking sector outcomes (for example, to bail out insolvent banks, decide on bank mergers or maintain significant State ownership). Regulation, informal or formal appears to be an important factor in the operation of banks, and therefore requires a close analysis on how it impacts the activities of banks.

Since the early nineteen seventies, the global financial system was generally characterised by regulatory limitations such as controls on interest rates and on the quantity of credit, restrictions on market access, and, in some cases, controls on the allocation of finance amongst alternative borrowers. The limitations served as a means to control the allocation of capital directly to preferred industries in countries that give substance to a "champion" policy. During these periods, restrictions served to control market access and competition persuaded by concerns over financial stability. The restrictions on interest rates were motivated by the Authorities' attempt to keep the cost of borrowing low (Cordero & Montecino, 2010).

The formation of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS or Basel Committee) in 1975 provided a market oriented approach to the regulation of banks. The Basel accord was established by the Governors of the Central Banks of the Group of Ten (G10) industrial countries namely: Belgium, Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States. These countries consulted and co-operated on economic, monetary and financial matters (BIS, 2018). The formation of the committee followed the crisis in the international currency and banking markets that notably led to the failure of the BankhausHerstatt in the then West Germany. The Committee, headquartered at the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) in Basel, Switzerland was established to enhance financial stability by improving the quality of banking supervision worldwide, and to serve as a forum for regular cooperation between its member countries on banking supervisory matters (BIS, 2018).

The capital requirements framework created in the context of the Basel Committee paved the way to the development of stronger competition in banking. Market discipline and competition have now substituted the other more interventionist

and discretionary instruments of regulation. It is unquestionable that banks all over the world now face greater competition, both from new entrants in the banking sector and from other financial companies (BIS, 2018).

The BIS (2018) agrees with the work of Heimler (2006), that the most important rationale for regulation in banking is to address concerns over the safety and stability of financial institutions, the financial sector as a whole, and the payments system. Mandatory deposit insurance schemes are introduced in order to avoid bank runs. Capital adequacy requirements make sure that banks do not become over-exposed to risks. Lender of last resort interventions eases temporary illiquidity. However, the BIS (2018) argue that the Basel 2 framework has not eliminated the need for regulation. Its objective is to adopt more market-oriented regulatory measures. The above-mentioned developments, supported by the continuous review in the Basel framework, underpin the rationale for this paper.

Since its inception, the Basel Committee has expanded its membership from the G10 to 45 institutions from 28 jurisdictions. The number seems to be growing as the sophistication in the banking environment increases. Starting with the Basel Concordat, first issued in 1975 and revised several times since, the Committee has established a series of international standards for bank regulation, most notably its landmark publications of the accords on capital adequacy, which are commonly known as Basel I, Basel II, Basel III and, most recently, Basel IV. It appears as though the introduction, implementation and continuous revision of the framework could arguably introduce the rigour in regulation and supervision of banks. The speed and the number of regulatory changes that banks are required to adhere to appear to be increasing. Banks are investing resources and valuable time to meet the regulatory and supervisory requirements. It is therefore, imperative to analyse what the implications of these continuous changes have on the performance of banks.

Zgarni and Fedhila (2018) agree with the argument by the Bank of International Settlement (BIS, 2018) however, they hold that there is a succession of crises that have occurred despite this strict prudential regulation. It is therefore, of particular interest to study the impact of regulation and supervision on banks as it contributes to policy making; and might have unintended consequences.

Until very recently, when the fragility of the banking sector is tested, resulting in crises in the sector, regulations including the imposition of stringent capital requirements and risk appetites are immediate measures in the regulators toolbox. The imposition of minimum capital requirements on banks is one of the pillars of macro-prudential regulation that cushions excessive risk taking (Heimler, 2018).

Authorities are increasingly following this feat in African economies as they grapple with the global financial regulation and supervisory regimes. It appears that African countries are implementing the new regulation regimes on positive sentiments from the developed countries. It is therefore, imperative that studies on the impacts of these regulations that were developed and imposed based on issues that mainly emanate from developed economies be performed in Africa. This could assist regulators in adapting the "international" regulations in a way that benefits their citizens.

III. THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical literature review

Gale (2010) contends that when general equilibrium effects are taken into account, it is not clear that higher capital requirements will reduce the level of risk in the banking system. It is therefore, essential, that regulators take a clear view and understanding of the impacts of the reforms intended to mitigate banks' operations, as this could lead to unintended consequences to the profitability of banks and their risk profile. This is in contrast to the findings of the work performed by Deloitte (2019) in their Financial Services regulatory outlooks. Deloitte pronounced that, nearly ten years after the financial crisis, the long shadow it has cast has started to fade. With the exception of the final stages of Basel III, most post-crisis prudential policies have now been decided, and banks in particular are now much better capitalised and more liquid than before the crisis. Amid varied approaches and timetables to national implementation of agreed prudential reforms, attention is now more acutely focused on culture and governance, the challenges of new technology, and emerging economic, market and operational risks. Banks need to be prepared to respond to this shifting focus and the new demands that it will place on them.

Having stated that, Schmidt (2002) found some evidence that one of the competing requirements for the success of any business in any economy is the existence of a favourable regulatory environment. This is also evidenced in the works of

Thatcher and Stone (2002) and Moran (2002) which stated that regulations can be either a boon or bust to the profitability and risk profile of banks.

In addition, empirical evidence from Kerwer (2005), King (2005) and Quaglia (2005) suggests that environmental regulations deter entry into industries where the requirements for regulatory compliance activities are high. This does not seem to be a major problem in the banking sector; however, the industry is increasingly operating from environmentally friendly buildings. This stance informs their investing principles, which in turn affects the bank's risk profile, and profitability.

Gale (2010) further observed that, tougher bank regulations may have positive benefits; they may reduce the consequences of market freezes, they may encourage banks to become smaller to avoid "systemic" capital requirements, and they may reduce contagion, but they may not be relied on to reduce the risk of bank failure. This aligns with the work of Oke (2006) that observed the inconsistency in monetary and regulatory policies as major setback to banks' stability.

Mishkin (1997) viewed that forging a strong bank supervision system will be one way out of financial crisis, while Ogunleye (2005) summarised the rationale for banks' regulation as efficiency, diversity of choice, competition, stability of financial system, macroeconomic stability and development, and social objectives. This view is aligned with that of the World Bank (1986), that argues that good regulation and supervision will minimise the negative impact of moral hazard and price shocks on the financial system leading to a reduction in bank distress and failure.

As stated above, Llewellyn (1986) describes prudential regulation as a body of specific rules or agreed behaviour, either imposed by the government or external agency or self-imposed by explicit or implied agreement with the industries that constrain the activities in the industry. In terms of policy thrust therefore, the banking sector's reforms are expected to build and foster a competitive and healthy financial system to support development and avoid systemic distress.

Balogun (2007) stated that banking sector reforms is interpreted to mean embarking on a comprehensive process aimed at substantially improving the financial infrastructure, strengthening the regulatory and supervisory framework to address the issue of low capitalisation and a structured financing for cheap credit to the real sector and financial accommodation for small and rural credit schemes. Studies have shown that the objectives of financial sector reforms are broadly the same in most countries of sub-Saharan Africa (Balogun, 2007). These are summarised to include market liberalisation for promotion of more efficient resource allocation, expansion of savings mobilisation base, promotion of investment and growth through market based interest rates.

These studies also mean the improvement of the regulatory and supervision framework, fostering healthy competition in the provision of service and, above all, laying the basis for inflation control and economic growth (Balogun, 2007). Regulation may also reduce industry risks through the elimination of weak banks and create better diversification opportunities (Berger, 2000). Balogun and Berger made some important points, but these studies appear to take new developments in regulations into consideration. The cost of regulatory compliance is also missing in the arguments made in these studies.

On the other hand, the opponents of regulation argue that consolidation could increase banks' propensity toward risk taking through increases in leverage and off balance sheet operations. In addition, scale economies are limited as larger entities are usually more complex and costly to manage (De Nicoló, 2003).

Empirical literature review

When the performance of banks and other financial institutions are assessed, it is mainly based on the analysis and assessment of how certain key indicators perform. Indicators such as Return on Assets, Return on Equity, and other financial ratios are used. The ability of the bank to generate high profits at a fraction of costs (lowest amount of input-efficiency) on the other hand, could be conducted through the application of parametric or non-parametric frontier techniques (Kale, Ken & Selimler, 2015).

Delis, Molyneux and Pasiouras (2011) worked on the relationship between the regulatory and supervision framework and the productivity (profits) of banks in 22 countries over the period 1999–2006. The work concluded that regulation

and proper supervision of banks promote private monitoring and restrictions on banks' activities (securities, insurance, real estate and ownership of non-financial institutions), which in turn had a positive impact on efficiency.

On the other hand, regulations relating to capital requirements and official supervisory power did not have a significant impact on productivity. If this is the case, the results of financial reforms coordinated by the G20 and Basel III framework need to be analysed carefully. The myriad of regulations that the two international bodies require their members to implement appear to be geared towards better capitalisation of large banks. In addition, the special report: International Banking compiled by the Economist (2017) argues that many banks are in much better shape since the crisis a decade ago; however the gains are not evenly spread, particularly in Europe. These mixed findings again affirm the need for further studies in this area.

The work performed by Lee and Chih (2013) analysed the effects of regulations that included the imposition of a strict capital base, liquidity and provisions and leverage ratios. The work concentrated on banks within the ambit of the China Banking Commission and analysed the effects that Basel III regulations have on the profits and risk taking activities of banks for the period 2004 to 2011. The researchers applied an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression to establish the relationship between regulation and risks. The study found that the effect of regulation impacts small and big banks differently. It showed that the current ratio did not affect the risk taking by banks. This is partly in contrast to the findings of Delis (2014) above and confirms the mixed findings of studies on the impacts of regulation and supervision on the profits and risk profile of banks. It appears that different methodologies, different scopes, method, data and the jurisdictions where these studies are done are not uniform; this argument could be made for formulae and variables that are used by different researchers from different jurisdictions to include general and distinctive variables to their study. This could be construed to be a signal of paucity in the work performed in the area, especially in emerging markets of which Africa is a part.

Gaganis and Pasiouras (2013) studied the relationship between the efficiency of bank profit and supervisory frameworks imposed by central banks using approximately 4000 commercial banks operating in 80 countries for the period 2000 to 2006. The researchers applied the intermediation approach and stochastic frontier model. The results of the study indicated that profits of banks operating under countries with too many supervisory regimes are impacted negatively (i.e. the profits decreased). In addition, the study concluded that efficiency decreased as the number of financial sectors that were supervised by the central banks increased.

With the pace and number of regulations being implemented in the banking sector for the duration of this study, an argument could be made that under the current operating environment the results could have been different. However, this study will remain none the wiser until more work is performed in this area. Barth (2013b) examined whether bank regulation, supervision and monitoring enhanced or impeded banks' operating efficiencies based on three worldwide surveys sponsored by the World Bank covering 4,050 banks observations in 72 countries over the period 1999 to 2007. The study examined the relationship between bank regulation, supervision and monitoring, and bank efficiencies. They found that tighter restrictions on bank activities were negatively associated with banks' efficiencies, while greater capital regulation stringency was marginally and positively associated with banks' efficiencies. The study also found that a strengthening of official supervisory power was positively associated with bank efficiency only in countries with independent supervisory authorities. In addition, independence coupled with a more experienced supervisory authority tends to enhance bank efficiency.

Barth (2013a) presented a database of bank regulation and supervision in more than 180 countries for the period of 1999 to 2011 based on the World Bank's survey. The study constructed indices from answers from the survey and measured the key features of the regulatory and supervisory approaches to what banks could do. Key features include: capital standards, the powers of official supervisory agencies, regulations on the entry of new banks, the degree to which the authorities encouraged the monitoring of banks by private investors, the nature of the deposit insurance regime, and an assortment of other policies towards banks. The database also enabled cross-country and cross-time comparisons. The study found that, in spite of some convergences, there still exists a substantial heterogeneity in bank supervisory policies across countries, and it was still possible to observe an opposite direction between different countries about a regulation.

Barth (2012) argued that although many countries had reformed their bank-regulatory regimes in the last twelve years, there was no evidence for better improvements. Many countries had obeyed the Basel guidelines and strengthened capital regulations and empowered supervisory agencies; but existing evidence did not support that this would improve

the banking-system stability, enhance the efficiency of intermediation, or reduce corruption in lending. It is therefore important to study the impact that regulation and supervision have on banks, to contribute to the body of knowledge that will assist regulators and policymakers on the development, review and implementation of regulations.

Kumar, Charles, and Mishra (2016) evaluated the performances of the Indian banking sector for the post-reform period and global financial crisis between 1995 and 2009. They indicated that the reforms resulted in a positive change in the total factor productivity of the banking sector through technological changes. Meanwhile, Sanchez (2013) concluded that the financial liberalization had led to productivity increases because of the technological progress rather than enhanced technical progress in Latin America during the period 1996 to 2007.

According to Barth, Caprio and Levine (2001) there is evidence that the literature on regulation and supervision of banks in the developing countries is biased towards the way things are done in the Consultants' home countries due to their lack of information on practice in other countries. Experts on the subject tend to use the supervisory and supervision framework of their country of origin as a benchmark model for developing countries. Africa, as part of the developing economies of the world falls within the parameters of such biasness. The trio further indicated that there is anecdotal evidence accumulated over the years that suggests that an astonishingly high degree of accuracy could be obtained merely by knowing each consultant's country of origin.

The literature on the impact of regulation and supervision on the activities of banks concentrates on developed economies in the main (Deng, Casu & Ferrari, 2014). Although large economies in Africa such as South Africa and Nigeria boast "sophisticated banking systems", they tend not to be included in studies of this nature. Despite the Regulators and Supervisors (Basel, FSO, 2016.) in some African countries operating within international frameworks in monitoring and supervising their banks, the literature in this area on Africa is scarce.

International studies on the subject offer diverse evidence. Barth (2004) assessed the relationship between regulatory and supervisory practices and banking sector development, efficiency and fragility on bank regulation and supervision among 107 countries. The results of the study raised some concerns regarding government policies that rely on direct supervision and regulation on banks activities. In this study, the results suggest that there is no statistically significant relationship between capital stringency, official supervisory power and bank performance. However, they found that the regulatory and supervisory practices, which work best to promote bank profitability and stability, insist on accurate information disclosure, empower private sector monitoring of banks, and foster incentives for private agents to exert corporate control. Using a cross-country setting, the authors highlighted that regulatory and supervisory regimes with these features have suffered fewer crises in the past two decades, have lower non-performing loans and stronger credit markets.

Barth's recent studies on the subject were during 2010, where further highlights on the impact of regulations on the activities of banks were provided. These studies indicated that stringency in the supervision of banks impacts negatively on the efficiency of the bank and restrictions on capital brings a marginal positive impact to the efficiency of the bank. In addition, the study found that although there is no significant relationship between official supervisory power and bank efficiency, there is a significant and positive relationship between the latter and supervisory authority independence.

In a study of ten publicly listed banks by Leaven and Levine (2009), in countries for which La Porta, Lopez-de-Silanes, Shleifer, and Vishny (1998) assembled data on shareholder rights, it was found that capital stringency has little impact on actual bank risk. In addition, capital requirements affect bank stability through their bank valuations, but do not have an independent effect on bank stability. In addition the Leaven and Levine study suggested that activity restrictions and deposit insurance increase bank risk, confirming the conclusions by Demircuc-Kunt and Detragiache (2002) and Barth et al. (2004,2006), while theoretically banking regulations and supervision might be expected to enhance profitability and decrease financial banking risk. Buch (2008), who used the database compiled by Barth (2001), found that the supervisory systems influence the overall risk of cross-bank mergers. They also concluded that the impact of banking regulations and supervision on performance depends on the factors of influence.

Chortareas (2012) investigated the dynamics between regulatory and supervisory policies and bank performance for a sample of European banks over the period 2000-2008. The investigation found that strengthening capital restrictions and official supervisory powers could improve the efficient operations of banks. The results also indicated that interventionist supervisory and regulatory policies such as private sector monitoring and restricting bank activities could result in higher

levels of inefficiency. That being the case, the beneficial effects of capital restrictions and official supervisory powers on banks' efficiency are more pronounced in countries with higher quality institutions. This is supported by the findings of a study by Lee and Hsieh (2013) that focused on Asian banks over the period 1994-2008, which pointed to a positive relationship between capital and profitability in Asian banks. The study concluded that the effects of the influencing factors should be taken into consideration.

Deng, Casu and Ferrari (2014) provided evidence that the literature on the impact of progress in the regulatory and supervisory reforms on banks' profitability focused on listed banks that operate in markets within Europe. This is in line with the findings from the work performed by Chortareas (2012), Delis (2011), Pasiouras (2009) and Haw (2010). The paucity of empirical studies in general makes the analysis of the African market particularly important from the regulatory and supervisory perspective (Triki, Kouki, Dhaou&Calice, 2017). In addition, Deng (2014) argues that the literature on the impact of regulation and supervision on the profitability and risk profiles of banks shows some consensus on the benefits of financial liberalisation as it encourages growth and eventually stimulates economic growth.

The literature on prudential regulation shows the impact on the profitability of banks to be mixed. There is a school of thought that argues that the regulation strengthens the stability of the financial system, thereby improving the operations of the banking sector. Another school argues that regulation hampers financial intermediation. However, Gorton and Winton (2010) brought the arguments of economic theory and suggest that regulation tools can impact on the effectiveness of financial intermediation through the imposition of stringent capital requirements. This could reduce the costs of borrowing by banks. This is due to the theory that banks that hold high capital reduce the risk of going bankrupt. By the same logic, imposition of minimum capital requirements could increase the cost of borrowing by banks. This could discourage banks borrowers, which could in turn affect the risk profiles of the bank negatively.

As indicated by Chortareas (2012), there is an increasing interest in the academic literature in analysing and evaluating the impact of bank prudential regulation on efficiency. To this end, the empirical outcomes are rather mixed. Chortareas(2012) further showed evidence that the current regulatory and supervisory frameworks impede the efficient operation of banks. The researcher believes this paper will also contribute to the literature and answers some of the academic interest informed in the literature and the work of Chortareas (2012).

IV. PROFITABILITY AND RISK PROFILES OF BANKS

Profitability

A study by Abdullah, Parvez and Ayreen (2014) looked at the factors that impact on the profitability of banks in Bangladesh by exploring the determinants of profitability of 26 banks listed in the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). The study categorized the determinants into three themes that are connected to the profitability of banks: those that are directly specific to the banks, the industry in general and the macroeconomic variables.

The study used return on assets (ROA) and net interest margin (NIM) as a proxy for profitability for reasons ranging from the assumptions that ROA explores the profits derived from the invested assets, whereas NIM is seen as the measure of the difference between interest revenues and interest costs. Although the study was performed on a single country, a reasonable number of banks were included and the researcher commended the study for including macroeconomic variables that consider the environments within which the banking system works; however, the study period appears to be short (about 4 years). This could be the disadvantage in the outcome of the study since the industry and the macroeconomic variables might take a longer period to show any material impacts on the independent variables, in this case, ROA and NIM. This argument is supported by the findings of the study that concludes that overall the banking specific variables appear to have a positive effect on the profitability of banks in Bangladesh, whereas the industry and macroeconomic variables such as higher taxation and higher banking assets to gross domestic product (GDP) appear to decrease profitability.

The study contributes to the body of knowledge on the rare literature on determining the banks' profitability in emerging markets. The rarity of studies of this nature has been highlighted by other researchers such as Aysan and Gunes (2007), Ali, Akhtar, and Ahmed (2011) whose studies on the profitability of banks in developing countries (of which Bangladesh is part) found challenges in finding relevant and "recent" literature.

The trio's study was performed on commercial banks in Pakistan with data collected for a short period from 2006-2009. The aim of the study was to analyse the effect of public and private variables on the profitability of banks in Pakistan. The findings are similar to those found by Addullah, Parvez and Ayreen (2014) in Bangladesh, although their study was performed almost four years later. The study was performed under similar circumstances, with ROE and ROA used as measures of profitability. The similarities of these studies, and their outputs are amazing, however, without casting a shadow of doubt on the study performed in 2014, it would have been expected that the changes in technology over the period between the two studies in two different countries would have impacted slightly on the macroeconomic variables and more on the banking specific variables.

Other earlier studies such as those on the internal factor analysis of the banking sector in Pakistan by Jayaid, Anwar, Zaman and Gafoor (2011) examined the profitability of 10 banks for a period of about four years with almost similar findings, although the proxy for profitability was the return on equity (ROE) and ROA. The study did not include industry variables, and similarly was performed over a short period, and therefore places a dim view on the findings for reasons stipulated above. Although a quick review of the background of the researchers shows that they are esteemed academics, working experience in the banking sector would have enriched their studies substantially. The inclusion of costs of banking and / or impairments could have impacted on the findings of the study.

This argument appears to be supported by a study by Akbas (2012) on the determinants of bank profitability on the Turkish banking sector by examining the impact of bank, industry and macroeconomic specific factors on the profitability of 26 commercial banks in Turkey over five years. This study found that the ratio of loan loss provisions to gross loans, the ratio of the total cost to total income, Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) for deposits and inflation, have statistical significance and negative relationship with return on assets. Similar findings were true when the return on equity (ROE) was taken as a measure of profitability.

The study followed the one previously done by Alper and Anbar (2011) where they examined bank and macroeconomic determinants of commercial bank profitability in Turkey. They excluded the industry-specific determinants and the results were slightly different although they also used ROA and ROE as proxies for profitability. The study, using a balanced panel dataset, suggests that profitability in banks can be improved through increasing bank size and non-interest income. This missed the point on the increase in costs and the risk brought by banks venturing too much into the business of banking. Besides, the theory that growth in the size of the bank should increase income is well known within banking, however, banks should be cautious towards organic growth, as inorganic growth might impact on the risk profile of banks.

El-Kassem (2017) investigated the main determinants of the profitability of six major lender banks using panel data from Qatar for the period 2008-2015. The study was an attempt to determine the effect of liquidity and risk variables on the explained variation of the bank's performance in Qatar. The data was sampled from the world Bankscope database. Although the study was performed in a relatively long period in comparison to other studies in that region, the period is still short relative to studies in developed countries. The study estimates the "return on average assets" (ROAA) as a function of independent variables that are liquidity and risk variables. It is not clear what the proxy of this variable represents, performance or profitability of banks in Qatar.

It appears as if the two are used interchangeably, and therefore should be richer if the introduction of a new variable and its representation is significantly explained to distinguish profitability and performance in banks. In conclusion, the study findings refer to performance and fail to discuss any determinants of profitability as it highlighted that the variation of the independent variable "total capital ratio %" significantly affects the variation in performance of banks in Qatar measured by ROAA.

The study by Abedin and Dawan (2016) used a panel data analysis to estimate the profitability of the banking sector in Bangladesh. The study evaluated a panel of 29 banks using the Panel Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) approach and random effect ordinary least squares (OLS) and found that loans and advances, human resources, efficiency and the growth of economic money supply have a positive impact on profitability, whilst investment in government securities and shares has a significant negative impact. The findings of the study are as expected; however, it could have been richer, if it analysed the variables and determined how they behave in the estimation of profitability equation during the period of the study.

From the literature reviews, it appears that there are several variables within the banks' financial statement that can be used as a proxy for Profitability. The internal variables that banks are utilizing for determining profitability are the return on equity (ROE), that measures the rate of return that shareholders receive for investing their capital into banks. The return on assets (ROA) shows the efficiency of the management of banks in managing the assets of the bank into net earnings. Net Interest Margin (NIM) and Net Non-Interest Margin (NNIM) measures how the management of interest received from banks' activities such as deposits and borrowings is realised into net earnings. The latter deals with interest received from the non-banking activities of the bank. The pieces of literature appear not to delve much into the impact of risks that these variables are 'hit' against to realise the Profits such as the obvious inherent ones like credit and market risks. With the increase and fast-paced technological development and globalisation, operational risk has grown and its cost is significant in the determination of profitability in banks. Furthermore, regulators and policymakers appear to be concerned by developments in the sector and therefore impose new regulations – to the detriment of profitability in banks. Regulations are concerned when bank's credit exposures increase, which speaks to the profile of the banks.

Risk Profile

McKinsey and Company's (2015) study found that policymakers worldwide have united behind efforts to increase financial institutions' minimum capital requirements and so limit leverage, hoping to reduce the likelihood of future banking crises. This is in response to the 2008 to 2009 global banking crisis. To date, the debates over capital requirements continue, with major implications for the industry and the economy; however, there have been few specifics on which ratios should be targeted or what levels.

Policymakers traditionally measure and regulate bank risk at a micro-prudential level where individual banks are assessed. However, post the 2008 to 2009 global financial crises, the Basel committees appear to have acknowledged that banks and the banking system should be regulated and supervised from a macro-prudential perspective focusing on the stability of the financial system as a whole (Acharya, 2009; BCBS, 2010). Recently macro-prudential risk measures have become a standard tool to assess the resilience of banks and banking systems.

The BCBS (2010) highlights a set of recommendations on bank regulations, concerning capital for credit risk, market risk, and operational risk. Value-at-Risk (VaR) and Expected shortfall (ES) are two standard risk measures and are recommended by Basel II and Basel III respectively. Other market-based methods, such as the Capital Assets Pricing Model (CAPM), are also widely used to measure individual bank risks. It is common to measure risk using banks' share price (return), which can link banks' risk with return. These market-based risk measures are widely applicable to listed banks. As a complement or where banks are not listed, bank risk can also be estimated with accounting data (Haldane, 2009). Examples of traditional accounting data-based risk measures include equity-to-asset ratio, the ratio of non-performing loans (NPL) to total assets and the z-score. However, during the 2008 to 2009 financial crisis, it was argued that these traditional measures failed to fully capture bank risks, especially downside risk (Haldane, 2009).

Experience shows that only a few international banks operating in Africa are at such an advanced stage and therefore are required to implement advanced regulatory approaches in measuring risks by their home country. It is therefore prudent to take the uniqueness of banks, and developments in African countries into considerations when selecting variables for studies on banks operating in Africa.

V. REGULATION, SUPERVISION AND EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN AFRICA

According to Triki, Dhaoui and Calice (2010), there are two schools of thought in the literature on the regulation and activities of banks in Africa. There is a school of thought that samples cross country data to estimate the level of efficiency and its basic determinants. On the other hand, another school of thought uses the country case studies to investigate the impact of regulatory reforms on bank performance and efficiency.

Regulations and supervisory reforms seem to be increasing in developing economies. With the connectedness of business and macroeconomic developments across the globe, policymakers are challenged to make sure that imposition of new regulatory and supervisory reforms assists the banking sector positively in being stable and profitable. This is important for the sector in Africa, which tend to take the lead of the developed countries and therefore might implement "good" regulations and policies developed, based on experiences and contexts different from theirs. Regulators in Africa should ascertain that the impact of policies adopted from developed economies do not have adverse effects on banks in their jurisdictions.

Many financial commentators and economists' comments indicate that the 2007 financial crisis did not affect African economies directly. This is due in part to the continent not participating in some of the activities that led to the crisis. In addition, some of the countries such as South Africa have good infrastructure and the financial system in general is respected internationally. Although, the global financial crises impacted these economies, their role in the causation of the crisis is arguable. The idiosyncratic variables of the economies in the continent provide researchers with a good laboratory within which to analyse and understand the impact of regulatory and supervisory reforms on banks' profitability and risk profile (Triki, Dhaoui&Calice, 2010).

VI. Conclusion

Studies on the performance of banks, risk profile, regulations and supervision differ from jurisdiction to jurisdiction. In some instances, the methodology and equations utilised in the calculations of banks' performances and /or profitability are not uniform. The variables appear to differ on the basis of the size of the banks understudy and products offered. The jurisdictions and the period of the study appear to have material impact on the outcome of studies.

Having reviewed the literature, it is evident that studies on the profitability and risk profile of banks should identify and uniform dependent and independent variables. Such variables should take the cost of regulation, supervision and their implementations into consideration including the consideration of fixed effect variables to cater for the uniqueness or idiosyncratic aspects in a selected country. Whatever countries and banks implement in the quest to meet the requirements of global regulatory bodies, should be fit for purpose and not be a one-size-fits-all.

The global financial crises persuaded authorities globally to reform their regulatory and supervision frameworks. The intention tends to be the absorption of the eventual shocks to the banking sector and eventually to mitigate against future banking crises. However, countries need to understand, what other authorities are doing in mitigating the crises through regulatory and supervisory reforms taking into consideration the idiosyncrasies of their economies and their banking environment. Studies on the impact of regulation and supervision indicate that regulation has effects on the profitability and risk profile of banks. However, the impact of such regulation and supervision is dependent on economic factors of the environment where banks are operating such as macro and micro economic factors, among others. The literature on bank regulation and supervision further shows that the conflicting empirical evidence warrants further research, specifically in developing countries.

Wolff (2013) found that the emerging regulatory framework following the global financial crisis is clearly relevant for Africa, as more African countries integrate into the global economy and for institutional learning. Therefore, future studies in Africa should consider specific circumstances of selected African countries to allow policymakers to make proper choices when developing regulations and regulatory frameworks.

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